

Role of One District One Product In Viksit Bharat

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Abstract

Viksit Bharat@2047 is a vision of Prime Minister Narendra Modi of making a developed and prosperous Bharat by the year 2047 when the country will celebrate its 100th year of independence. Viksit Bharat is not only a slogan but the Sankalp, a commitment to rejuvenate the India and to create India as a well-developed economy. Viksit Bharat 2047 connects the different sectors of economy specially the youth, the farmers and the entrepreneurs who wants to brighten their future for the welfare of themselves and the country. Viksit Bharat 2047 aims to provide a facility of pucca house and piped water of every citizen, establishment of Jan aushadi Kendra, to adopt green and sustainable growth policies. Apart from all these benefits to strengthen the India's political relations with other countries and to maintain a healthy and co-ordial relation of the country with other nations of the world. To achieve the objective of making India a \$30 trillion economy by the vision is also the key objective of the country as India is growing rapidly by securing its position as 5th largest economy in the world today and will be the 3rd largest economy by 2027 as per the IMF reports. This time period is Amrit Kaal for India as India is transformed on many dimensions of development and there has been the massive expansion in social and economic infrastructure of India through various policies and schemes of the government.

Keywords

Viksit Bharat@2047, Rejuvenate, Entrepreneurs, Sustainable Growth Policies, Amrit Kaal.

Introduction

The population of India has reached about 1.42 billion, as providing the potential for corresponding economic growth and demographic standardization. As soon the population of India becomes the global super power, it is imperative for the government of India to hold the responsibility for welfare of masses.so, for the welfare and wellbeing of the people, government of India loads lots of scheme.one of the best initiative of government of India is Viksit Bharat @2047.in the interim budget 2024, Finance Minister Nirmala Sitharaman stated about the Prime Minister Narendra Modi's vision about Viksit Bharat @2047.The main objective behind the implementation of Viksit Bharat is the transformation of the country into the developed nation by enhancing and empowering its four pillars of development. The four pillars of the Viksit Bharat are Yuva, Garib, Mahila and Kisan.Viksit Bharat is an opportunity for the achievement of prosperous Bharat in accordance with the modern infrastructure and various methods to achieve the best potentiality of citizens of India.

The vision of Viksit Bharat can be achieved better with the implementation of One District One Product Scheme. The One District One Product Scheme was launched in 2018, by Hon'ble Chief Minister Yogi Adityanath Ji on the occasion of Uttar Pradesh Diwas for the betterment and enhancement of local handicraft items of Uttar Pradesh and to promote the art and culture of traditions of the state. The main purpose behind the implementation of the scheme is to provide the financial assistance and enhancement of skills in young entrepreneurs and to provide them the sense of dignity and reputation in their artistic work and also for the achievement of Atma Nirbhar Bharat.

The Viksit Bharat @2047 Scheme is outlined by Prime Minister Narendra Modi with the vision of empowering the youth of India. The vision of Viksit Bharat@2047 can be achieved by

promoting the youth of the country and there is a need to implement fundamental and radical changes in the governance of Indian Universities and higher education institutions, till the 100th anniversary of independence. There are various factors of development such as economic prosperity, environmental sustainability, social advancements and effective governance. Helping and promoting MSMEs and young

entrepreneurs is also the objective of [Viksit Bharat@2047](#). Thus, for the enactment of the vision, the ministry of finance has offered the fund of Rs.75000 crore as a 50-year interest free loan to the state governments to obtain their milestones linked reforms.

The time period is like an Amrit Kaal for India, as India is developing in various sectors, and various schemes are launched in India so that our country will mark a remarkable impression in the world. The urban areas of India as well as rural India is also transforming. For the betterment of poor and to strengthen the economy of the nation, Pradhan Mantri Garib Kalyan Anna Yojana, Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana, Jan Dhan Yojana and MNRGA for the welfare and development of the nation.

One District One Product (ODOP) Scheme was launched in 2018 to by Hon'ble chief minister Yogi Adityanath Ji on the occasion of Uttar Pradesh Diwas. The scheme was launched to promote the handicrafts items of Uttar Pradesh. Each district is classified as the producer of the product, which is selected based on their specialty and uniqueness in that area. The emphasis lay upon the selected product, so that the product gets awareness and acceptability in national as well as international market.

The ODOP scheme was made up with a budget of 25 crore rupees and it provides various assistance to the young entrepreneurs to boost their startup. Thus, with the implementation of ODOP scheme government provides opportunity to the new entrepreneurs to newly established startups to globalize their product and thus to contribute in the export formation of the country. With the complimentary implementation of ODOP scheme and Viksit Bharat, India can be on the path of Viksit Bharat.

Kanpur city is the largest Centre of leather industry in the country. A variety of leather products like footwear, belts, purses, slippers, garments, saddles are made here. Kanpur city contributes over 20% of the total leather and leather goods export of India. The products made here are exported to various countries including several US and European countries. As according to the reports of Council for Leather Products (CLE) and Central Leather Research Institutes (CLRI) the total export for the year 2003-04 was Rs 1636 crore which increased by 2000 times over a short span of time .(Source: Kanpur Online) The main reason behind the growing popularity and importance of leather industry is that it provides employment to over 2 lakh people within the city of Kanpur.

Objective of study

1. To identify the economic contribution of One District One Product Scheme.
2. To examine the role of One District One Product Scheme for the accomplishment of objective of [Viksit Bharat@2047](#).

Review of Literature

Tanveer Bano and Anila Varghese (2023) analyzed that Viksit Bharat vision will achieve significant success and ensuring sustainability for future prospects. As the vision is a crucial element for transforming India as a developed nation by 2047, when the country will be celebrating the centenary of its freedom.

Altat Hussain Padder (2023) investigated that Viksit Bharat 2047 is not only a slogan but a Sankalp to make a developed nation by 2047 with various aspects of development such as by providing various medicines through Jan Aushadi Kendra, by providing dimensions of education to every student to achieve intelligence and excellence empowering women farmers with the help of drones , provide a pucca house and piped water to the people and many much more and thus achieve the objective of \$30 trillion economy by 100th year of independence.

J. Lakshmi Narayana (2024) examined in their research paper that the Viksit Bharat initiative aims to complement the vision of unwavering recognition and dedication towards the comprehensive and sustainable development for the collective aspirations by 2047 with the evolution of infrastructure development, healthcare facilities, environmental sustainability, research and development, education campaigns, and technology transformation.

Sumer Khajuria (2024) analyzed that for the development of Viksit Bharat the Modi government has introduced several initiatives and schemes for social advancement in India by introducing the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan, Skill India Mission, Jananni Suraksha Yojna, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Campaign, One District One Product Scheme and in the area of women empowerment. This includes to overcome the inequality in area of educational facilities, healthcare facilities, gender discrimination and other necessary services.

Methodology

In this paper the research methodology used for the purpose of analyzing and investigating the contribution of ODOP Scheme in the accomplishment of Viksit Bharat's objective will be Descriptive type research, as it is to be noted that the process behind the descriptive research includes an expected approach towards a need or condition, which is acceptable for monitoring of trends and planning according to the available resources. Exactly, the problem of examining the future trends and expected outcomes in the study of Viksit Bharat in India specifies the relationship among the various resources that are available for the better implementation of the scheme.

Sampling Procedure - The sampling method available for this approach is Simple Random Sampling. Simple Random Sampling is a procedure of selecting the sample drawn from the population and provides an assurance that each member in a group has an equal chance of being selected for the response. This simple random sampling involves various methods such as being answered on well-prepared questioners and survey reports which is basically designed according to the qualitative and quantitative approach.

Sample Size – The sampling size used for this study is 150 approximate.

Data Collection –

Primary Data – The primary data used for the purpose of collecting data is the coherent method of preparing surveys and open ended and closed ended questionnaires and interviews.

Secondary Data – The secondary data for the attainment of data will be collection of various records and reports from concerned authorities and journals and articles from recognized websites and newspapers.

Analytical Tools - The analytical tools which will be used are descriptive analysis, correlation and t-test.

Analysis

For the purpose of knowing about the facts and observations related to the project area, here are some of the list of informations necessary to know about the respondents such as their age, income level, occupation, their conceptual knowledge about the key terms and their perception related to the ODOP Scheme and Viksit Bharat.

**Table No. 1
Age and Gender wise Respondents**

Age Group	No. of Respondents	Gender	
		Male	Female
Below 20	06	4	2
21 -40	81	38	43
41 - 60	63	21	42

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: The study collects responses from the below 20 years age group and the responses collected are 6, out of which 4 respondents are male and 2 respondents are female. The samples collects responses from 21-40 age group are 81 out of which 38 are male and 43 are female respondents. From 41-60 age group there are total 63 responses, which denotes that 21 are male respondents and 42 are female respondents.

**Table No. 2
Educational Qualification**

S.No.	High school & Below	Intermediate	Undergraduate	Postgraduate	Other	Total
Educational Qualification	0	0	19	94	37	150

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: As the samples collected from the various participants the reports presents that the candidates qualified as post-graduation are representing the 63% of the total population. The under-graduate participants are only the 13% of the population whereas the participants which have some other qualification are 25% of the total population.

**Table No. 3
Occupation**

S.No.	Non – Salaried Employee	Salaried Employee	Total
Occupation	44	106	150

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: the non-salaried participants are 29% and the salaried participants are 71% of the total population.

**Table No. 4
Income Level**

S. No.	Below 20,000	21,000-50,000	51,000-1,00,000	Above 1,00,000	Total
Income Level	56	50	25	19	150

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: from the samples collected from the population it is depicted that the participants getting salary between the ranges from 21,000 to 50,000 are only 50 which forms only about 33% of the total population. The salary group between 51,000 to 1, 00,000 is only 25 which means the 17% of the total population. Only the 13% of the total population has income above 1, 00,000, while the population which has below than 20,000 rupees salary shows the 37% of the total population.

**Section -2
General Awareness**

General Awareness	Yes	No
About ODOP Scheme	131	19
About GDP	150	0
About Per Capita Income	125	25
About impact of poverty	150	0
About infrastructure development	144	6
About impact of technology	144	6
About economic growth of India	150	0

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: From the various responses collects from the respondents it is to be analyzed that about 90% of the respondents know very much about the general abbreviations as such some basic words like ODOP Scheme, about GDP, or what are the consequences of technological impact. The population is very much familiar about economic growth and per capita income of country.

Sub Section -1

Questions	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Fairly distribution of goods & services	7	12	0	112	19
super specialization	6	19	19	94	12
Labour involvement	12	19	19	69	31
Solely responsible	19	25	25	50	31
Empowering the ODOP Products	25	31	12	69	12
Societal well being	12	0	25	100	12
Identify one unique product	0	37	12	87	12
Competition with International Markets	12	56	19	50	12
Biasedness in one production	19	19	31	69	12
Development of whole economy	0	37	12	87	12
Negative influence on ODOP	19	50	37	31	12
Labour classes participation	0	44	25	69	12
Burden from local entrepreneurs	6	7	25	100	12
Tariffs & trade taxes	6	25	31	63	25
Development of identified products	0	6	12	63	69

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: From the responses collected from various respondents it is to be concluded that there are % people are agreed with the basic questions such as they are agree on the statement that ODOP can fairly distribute the overall development of goods & services. Some are agreed that ODOP scheme can successfully implement the super specialization and labour participation in various departments.

Conclusion

The ODOP Scheme focuses on a more detailed approach to boost economy and to create employment opportunities and thus to maximize the exports by promoting the local and small scale artisans. The scheme also the economic growth of Uttar Pradesh of becoming a \$1 trillion economy, fascinated as well as helps the artisans by obtaining GI tags for their products as to uplift the identity and quality. The ODOP initiative is focused on exhibiting the innovation of the Honable Prime Minister of India to implement balanced regional development of the country.

1. One District One Product Scheme has the great potential to provide jobs and to empower the weaker sections of the society. This ODOP Scheme has its strong impact on the entrepreneurial development and thus they create a remarkable impression on achieving the objectives of Viksit Bharat.
2. The One District One Product Scheme has its broad viewness on the major obstacles of the economy. Even in the tough times of corona pandemic, this ODOP Scheme has various options to provide employment opportunities to the local and rural people to empower them by giving them training programmes related to their marketing assistance and supplying them with so much of investment opportunities and financial assistance for their welfare and thus they contribute in achieving the core objectives of Viksit Bharat.
3. However, this One District One Product has its various benefits but still it has some loopholes or we can say that there are certain defficiencies which need to be addressed for its successful implementation.
4. The One District One Product Scheme has to be spread evenly in all the sections of the society. As the rural people and the other weaker sections are not properly aware and get educated for this scheme and thus they dont know about that how to get benefitted from this scheme.

5. Also in India the people has very few knowledge about the financial matters and they are not aware about the Government' initiative related to their start-ups and entrepreneurial development.
6. In spite of so many drawbacks, if the ODOP Scheme is well implemented and evenly distributed in all the segments of the society then it would be much beneficial for the development of the country and also in achieving the objectives of Viksit Bharat.

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